

UNIVERSITY MANAGEMENT REFORM AND THE NEED FOR NEW APPROACHES

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Annotation: In this article, the training of qualified and competitive personnel in the higher education system is an urgent socio-economic issue, and the introduction of new approaches to the organization and management of educational activities in the higher education system, personnel training and continuous education system, the dynamics of development and structural changes of state and non-state educational institutions are expressed.

Key words and phrases: higher education, leaders-employees, modern worldview, scientific-theoretical views, continuous education, management tasks, perfect person, educational standards, civil society, scientific-methodology.

INTRODUCTION

The need to reform the management of higher education institutions in Uzbekistan and introduce new approaches to it is increasing day by day. Implementation of management tasks is carried out using various methods. Therefore, the main criterion that determines the need to organize management, i.e. management activities, is the goal set before a person or institution, to achieve it, setting tasks, planning activities in advance, choosing guidelines for implementation, according to the content and essence of the tasks, it consists in selecting the executors and distributing the tasks to be performed, coordinating the activities of the participants in the process organized to achieve the set goal. The concept of control is usually described as the transition of a system from one state to a better state. It is necessary to pay attention to two aspects here. The first aspect is management in order to maintain the system and support its stability (administrative management). The second aspect is management that ensures the transition of the system to a new quality state, that is, continuous development.

Also, managers and employees of the educational institution should master the functional aspects of management, achieve labor productivity, approach their work responsibly, be able to direct the team towards the goal, adapt the management of the educational institution to internal and external changes, introduce innovative innovations. it is necessary to have the necessary knowledge, skills and qualifications to improve the use of innovative technologies in management.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

On the basis of the experience gained in the field of higher education, the regulatory and legal documents of the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan are constantly being improved. PQ-3775 of June 5, 2018 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On additional measures to increase the quality of education in higher education institutions and

ensure their active participation in comprehensive reforms implemented in the country" to determine the priority directions of the systematic reform of higher education in the Republic of Uzbekistan, to raise the process of training highly qualified personnel with modern knowledge and high moral and ethical qualities to a new level in terms of quality, to modernize higher education PF-5847 of October 8, 2019 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On approval of the concept of the development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" in order to develop the social sphere and economic sectors based on advanced educational technologies issued a decree no. According to the decree, the implementation of the following in the higher education system is determined:

development of public-private partnership in the field of higher education, increasing the level of coverage with higher education from 50 percent based on the organization of activities of state and non-state higher education institutions in the regions, creating a healthy competitive environment in the field;

Turning the National University of Uzbekistan and Samarkand State University into the flagship of our country's higher education institutions;

at least 10 higher education institutions in the republic are included in the list of higher education institutions in the first 1000 places of the ranking of internationally recognized organizations (Quacquarelli Symonds World University Rankings, Times Nearer Education or Academic Ranking of World Universities), including Including the National University of Uzbekistan and Samarkand State University in the list of the first 500 higher education institutions;

step-by-step transfer of the educational process to the credit-module system in higher education institutions;

based on international experiences, introduction of advanced standards of higher education, including gradual transition from education focused on acquiring theoretical knowledge to an educational system focused on formation of practical skills in educational programs;

to raise the content of higher education to a new level in terms of quality, to establish a system of highly qualified personnel training that will contribute to the sustainable development of the social sphere and economic sectors, and will find their place in the labor market; etc.

In 2017-2021, the fourth direction of the Strategy of Actions on the five priority directions of the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan is directed to the development of the social sphere, and its fourth item is the development of the sphere of education and science: improvement of state policy; based on the introduction of international standards for the assessment of the quality of education and teaching, it is to increase the quality and efficiency of the activities of higher education institutions, to gradually increase the quotas for admission to higher education institutions. The introduction of continuous education in our republic management bodies are required to solve a number of tasks and constantly improve and develop them. In this case, it is important to provide the educational process with quality regulatory and legal documents in a timely manner.

The perspective of the country's development is determined, first of all, by the human resources potential and the level of its utilization. During the reforms carried out in our republic, special attention was paid to raising the quality of personnel training to a higher level. In order to ensure the effectiveness of scientific research in the higher education system,

the reforms carried out in our country to train specialists who meet the requirements of world educational standards and increase the level of scientific potential, studying the experience of developed and developing foreign countries, our republic It is necessary to raise their quality level and ensure their effectiveness based on scientific research, further development of scientific, educational and industrial cooperation based on the standards of the Ministry of Education.

The concept of management efficiency results from the interaction of management system and management process efficiencies. We will pay attention to the common and different aspects of the concepts of management system efficiency and management process efficiency. represents the result. It can be evaluated in terms of quantity and quality. Higher results of education compared to other educational institutions do not always indicate a higher quality of management in this educational institution. For example, if an educational institution has a strong material base, it can pay teachers a higher salary than in another educational institution due to additional sources of funding, ordinary education, which is deprived of all these benefits can ensure the quality of education is higher than in the institution. But the problem is how well each educational institution uses its available opportunities. The external effectiveness of the management system refers to the achievement of the goals of society, the state and employers. Evaluating the effectiveness of the management process is the main criterion for decision-making. Due to this, great attention is paid to the concept of efficiency in economics and management. In general, in order to achieve high results in the management process in the educational system, observation, conversation, modeling, analysis, synthesis, expert assessment, and hierarchical analysis methods are used. The use of the multi-criteria analysis method in evaluating the effectiveness of the management process of recommended educational institutions enriches the management of higher education institutions, academic lyceums and vocational colleges with new methods. The approach based on the method of analysis of hierarchies in evaluating the effectiveness of the management of educational institutions appears as an important tool in making appropriate decisions and leads to the improvement of the management process. This means that it has both theoretical and practical significance.

Positive and negative factors can be distinguished according to their impact on the institution. If the positive factors contribute to the increase in the management efficiency of the educational institution, the negative factors prevent a positive change in efficiency.

There are factors that equally affect the management efficiency of any educational institution. Among such universal factors, the following can be listed:

- ☒ the quality of the goals;
- ☒ the possibility of realistic realization of the goals, that is, their compatibility with the means of achieving the set goal;
- ☒ correct assessment of the current situation;
- ☒ to motivate the head of the institution and the employees towards the set goals;
- ☒ capacity and personal qualities of the head of the educational institution;
- ☒ the amount and quality of resources allocated to achieve the set goals;
- ☒ participation of state and society and collegial management bodies in making management decisions.

Also, the management process in the management system of educational institutions should be properly established, the concepts of its effectiveness should be clearly

distinguished, its content and essence should be revealed, the department rating model based on the method of hierarchies analysis in educational institutions should be developed, its Based on the methods of evaluating the effectiveness of the management process, the factors affecting the achievement of high results in the evaluation of the effectiveness of the educational institution are considered.

Assessment of the impact of the graduates of the educational system of economics on the development of the regional economy, determination of the relationship between the efficiency of the management process of educational institutions and the results of practical activities, improvement of management processes, training of economists in the field of education and its management. is important in making optimal decisions. The effectiveness of the management process is one of the main factors that ensure the success of an educational institution in the market of educational services. It is the effective management process that makes it possible to fully use all the resources of the institution and organization. Taking into account these aspects, the management process and its theoretical foundations in the educational system, as well as the concept of its effectiveness, theoretical and practical aspects of evaluation and evaluation indicators were determined. Also, in the higher education system, proposals were made to improve the method of integral assessment of the effectiveness of the management process of departments in the direction of economics, as well as to determine the factors affecting the management process, to show the highest level of superiority, the teaching and method of the departments of economics , made it possible to evaluate the effectiveness of management in scientific-research, spiritual-educational activities.

RESULTS

Today, many scientific works have been published on management culture and its role and importance in the life of a higher education institution. Among them, the scientific researches of several specialists in the field of educational institution management and some scientists who carried out scientific activities in this field are noteworthy for the fact that they are dedicated to the study of various aspects of the management culture in the educational institution. Taking into account the place of education in the life of society, it should be said that the problems of researching the unique management culture of the educational institution, the formation of the culture of management organization, and the practical use of the potential of the personnel reserve are considered urgent today.

In HEIs, the management culture is a management tool for the employees of the institution, as well as the entire pedagogical team. Using this management tool, the head of the educational institution forms a specific model of the behavior of pedagogues, ensures that a specific type of culture leads in his organization, increases its positive potential and uses it. Because there are several types of culture at the same time in the educational institution. It is worth noting that the growth of competition in the labor market and the demand for personnel training require the development of a part-active and entrepreneurial type of management in institutions.

The same approach was recognized by the employees of OTM. It was specially recognized that the comprehensive discussion direction of the organization, which is typical of the type of participatory management, corresponds to today's requirements. At the same time, it was emphasized that the solution of problems (with the help of open mutual cooperation), the expression of organizational principles of leadership (stimulation of

communication and cooperation) in these directions are fully compatible with the mission of the organization. For this reason, more attention is paid to the participative culture in the prospective type of organization management.

Another activity identified as a promising direction is the search for new creative approaches to solving persistent problems. It was explained that another type of management that should be developed with the help of this factor is based on entrepreneurship.

Another point that attracts attention is that the indicators of the bureaucratic management type, as they were in practice, remained the same in the future. As a reason for this, it can be shown that there is this culture in higher education institutions in the field of pedagogy.

In fact, the basis of the higher education system should be the bureaucratic culture, but its increase can strengthen formalism and negatively affect the level of creativity and freedom in the educational institution. Measures aimed at the formation of managerial competencies of the reserve of management personnel in the educational institution constitute a management tool for the behavior of the staff of the institution, as well as the entire pedagogical team.

Using this management tool, the head of the educational institution forms a clear model of the behavior of pedagogues, ensures the leadership of the type of management suitable for his goals in his organization, increases its positive potential and uses it.

In the early stages of the development of management theory in the higher education system, views based on scientific approaches to the management of educational systems were further developed in the 30s of the 20th century, and became widespread mainly in the United States, and the administrative methods of educational management during this period, by the end of this period, new The theory of management based on the principles of human relations, which made a radical change, began to develop. According to the results of the "Hawthorne experiment" of one of the founders of this theory, E. Mayo and his colleagues J. Homans, M. Follett, A. Maslow, F. Roethlisberger, social and psychological factors are more important than physical factors to labor productivity. proven to be effective.

According to the analysis, the theory of educational management has developed rapidly in foreign countries, in particular, Western European countries, the USA and Canada, Australia and New Zealand. During the long-term development and as a result of encountering several stages of change, it has become a scientific direction that occupies a special place in the field of the general theory of management.

Advanced foreign experiences show that all links of the education system are managed through effective information systems. The information system of educational management (TBAT) serves as a convenient method of effective management, planning, organization of education, collection of reliable data, their analysis and exchange of information between all levels. The implementation of TBAT not only provides effective organization and management of the educational system, but also creates the following conveniences for the participants and partners of the system: objective, up-to-date, complete information about the effectiveness, shortcomings and needs of the educational system, the activity of the institution and the pedagogical community. and reliable information is collected; based on this type of information, it serves to define and maintain the educational policy, to manage it, to evaluate its effectiveness and to introduce the necessary changes to it in a timely manner.

In the modern practice of Russian higher education, we observe the popularization of the ideas of university autonomy and institutional independence, which were formed as "two

sides of the same coin" throughout the history of the development of universities. Achieving current goals for modern education on the basis of these ideas requires, first of all, a deep understanding of them by all members of the academic community.

DISCUSSION

In this regard, the article attempts to compare the concepts of "autonomy" and "institutional independence" in connection with modern autonomy.

In the Lima Declaration of 1988, institutional independence is defined as "the freedom of members of the academic community to conduct research, study, discuss, produce, create, teach, contribute to the creation and transmission of knowledge through lectures and publications, individually or jointly." is defined as. In addition, such a broad understanding of the phenomenon of institutional independence, it was also seen as an educational trajectory in the formation of the freedom of teaching, research, financial and economic activities of the university, as well as the freedom of students. It is not for nothing that a number of regulatory documents of Russia in the field of visual education are distinguished by the use of the term "freedom" in the plural ("institutional independence"). Compared with the concept of "institutional independence", the term "autonomy" is used as a complex feature reflecting the independent, relatively independent activity of universities and their employees in the modern conditions of their education, in the conditions of the provided freedoms. Thus, from the point of view of researchers of modern universities, institutional independence is considered as a way to create the uniqueness of the university world, on the other hand, the development of the common European educational and scientific space is considered as one of the main indicators of the construction of knowledge.

This trend is primarily related to the globalization and democratization of modern society, which ensures the influence of international factors on institutional independence. Secondly, it is based on a significant increase in requirements for a person and as a subject of activity in a broad socio-cultural environment.

Today, the autonomy of universities is considered as freedom in creating curricula and quality standards, forming teaching staff, attracting students and determining the conditions of their work and study, as well as political autonomy (appointment), academic (institutional independence and z freedom) and financial (disposal of funds) complex is understood.

Thus, the concept of "institutional independence" is wider than the concept of "institutional independence" according to its content. At the institutional level, we can say that material autonomy reflects the independent existence of the university (autonomy acquired by the university), and procedural autonomy reflects its rights (autonomy given to the university or institutional independence). At the level of subjects of the educational process, institutional independence reflects the autonomy (their rights) that can be acquired by teachers and students as autonomous beings (autonomy in activity).

In actual practice, institutional independence and various types (forms) of independence are closely related and interdependent. Thus, "the freedom of research is determined by the availability of state or private funds for their implementation. If funds are allocated from public funds and there are no restrictions, in other words, if no specific goals are set, there will be more freedom." Accordingly, the higher the financial autonomy given to universities, the higher the level of academic freedom of teachers and students.

In contrast to institutional independence, the institutional independence of subjects of the educational process and the autonomy of the university, which represent the effectiveness

of institutional independence, are determined by a number of factors. Among them, first of all, external factors, including the level of institutional independence provided, state structure, educational legislation, financing, features of the university's educational environment, etc., play an important role. Secondly, for example, internal factors, readiness of teachers and students to act autonomously. The most important of these factors is the teacher's professional independence, which includes the whole set of aspirations, motives, attitudes, qualities and methods of the teacher's professional activity, which determines his behavior and self-development in a wider social context. - can determine cultural conditions.

At the same time, the professional autonomy of a university teacher not only ensures the autonomous activity of teachers, but also stimulates the development of autonomy among students, as well as a method of organizing the development of autonomy of the university as a whole. After all, as he rightly pointed out. G.S. Savolainen, "today, the teacher stands at the intersection of the needs of modern man and society, he works in the field of shaping the personal and professional self-determination of the young generation."

Thus, it is the autonomy of the subjects of the educational process that provides a stable connection between institutional independence and various types and forms of autonomy and allows (or does not allow) the mastering of teachers, students, and higher education institutions in general.) is the central link. different degrees of autonomy given to them. The considered relationships are graphically reflected in the table below.

In his speech at the forum in Palermo (September 1997), the Director General of UNESCO, Federico Mayor, stressed the importance of institutional independence in the development of university autonomy, and it is very important to focus on the "positive", responsible type. Autonomy capable of ensuring autonomy (... "freedom"): "... the general trend towards greater autonomy ... also requires universities to solve some of the tasks related to redefining the role of institutional independence.

For the described relationship between the levels of institutional independence and autonomy in higher education, it is characteristic that their ratio changes depending on the stages of development of society and universities. A developed democratic society encourages the development of institutional independence. Second, the educational environment of the university provides an opportunity for teachers and students to acquire a high level of autonomy, provided that the subjects have autonomy. In turn, the developed institutional independence of the subjects of the educational environment of universities helps to democratize and innovative development of the university education system and to implement institutional autonomy. And finally, in general, the autonomy mastered by teachers, students and universities is a factor of sustainable development of the state and the whole society.

Therefore, different levels of academic autonomy (one of them is institutional independence) are closely related and interconnected. At the same time, a characteristic feature of modern higher education is that the described relationship between the levels of institutional independence and autonomy in education is not limited only to the university and even the country. In this context, E.B. Pokladok and V.V. Spasskaya, today, despite the various forms of its existence, institutional independence has an international character and is an international privilege of university teachers.

Rector of the University of Barcelona J.M. Bricolla noted that "freedom of education is a reality of life in democratic European countries." As for autonomy, as we mentioned above,

several times in the history of the development of philosophical ideas, it was associated with the ability of a person to "go outside": autonomy is the ability of a person to "go beyond the framework of institutional culture." Due to this, the teacher's autonomy is based on a deep understanding of the socio-cultural context, which ensures the teacher's active work and self-development not only in the university educational environment, but also outside it. Thus, the autonomy of the teacher (as an active participant in interuniversity and international projects, including those who are outside the scope of the actual teaching of a certain subject at the university) allows not only to influence the development of certain aspects of the educational environment. university and students within the framework of formal education, as well as the development of the university, state and society in general (including in the wide field of non-formal and informal education).

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, on the one hand, the level and nature of the development of a certain country, as well as the level of development of human civilization in general, affect the level of development of the teacher's professional autonomy and the level of mastering the autonomy given to him. On the other hand, the developed autonomy of the teaching staff is able to ensure the realization of the academic rights and freedoms of the subjects of the university's educational environment, as well as their personal and professional self-development opportunities. Thus, the autonomy of teachers can be considered as an important factor in the democratization and innovative development of the university, individual state education system, and the development of the world educational and scientific space in a global sense.

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